

A systematic review of academic resilience in India and South Africa: What we know from quantitative studies

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Abstract:

This systematic review examines quantitative research on academic resilience in South Africa and India, two countries characterised by persistent educational inequalities. This review analyses how academic resilience is conceptualised and measured, the statistical methods used, and the protective factors associated with academic resilience among school-aged children and adolescents across 27 empirical studies from India and South Africa. Using Rutter's Risk and Protective Factors Framework as an organising lens, the review identifies factors associated with academic resilience. Across both countries, enjoyment of learning and family structure are consistent predictors of resilience, while other factors, including socio-emotional skills such as grit and learner confidence show more context-specific associations. However, Indian and South African studies differ significantly in their operationalisation of resilience and in the statistical methods used, restricting the accumulation of comparable evidence. We argue that there is a need for greater conceptual and methodological coherence in academic resilience research in these countries. Future comparative work would benefit from more harmonised definitions and measurement approaches, informed by context-sensitive theoretical frameworks that reflect the structural and institutional realities of low- and middle-income settings.

Keywords: resilience; inequality; socio-emotional skills; India; South Africa

1. Introduction

In societies marked by deep and persistent inequality, education is often the most viable - sometimes the only - pathway to upward social mobility (Iversen et al., 2019). This is especially true in India and South Africa, two countries whose complex histories of colonialism, institutional discrimination, and social stratification have left behind stark and enduring socio-economic divides. These divides are reflected in and reproduced by highly unequal education systems (Asadullah and Yalonetzky, 2012; Spaul, 2013). Yet, amidst these challenges, some learners manage to succeed academically against the odds. Understanding this phenomenon of academic resilience offers insights into how young people navigate and overcome structural barriers to learning, and point to what education systems can do to better support students in vulnerable contexts.

To explore academic resilience in these two unequal and historically complex contexts, this paper presents a systematic review of the empirical literature on academic resilience in South Africa and India. The review is guided by three core research questions: First, what are the key risk and protective factors that predict academic resilience in each country? Second, what similarities and differences emerge across these two countries with respect to these factors? Third, how do the methodological approaches adopted in existing studies support or detract from comparative analysis of academic resilience in these two countries? By synthesising evidence from both settings, the paper identifies levers to support academic resilience and examines how resilience operates within structurally unequal education systems. We also suggest potential avenues to advance scholarship on academic resilience in these two countries.

This review identifies a number of key risk and protective factors associated with academic resilience in South Africa and India, while also revealing substantial variation in how resilience is defined and measured across the two contexts. A few protective factors emerge consistently across studies in both countries - notably, enjoyment of school and living with at least one biological parent. This highlights the importance of

both learner engagement and stable home environments in supporting resilience. However, many other factors showed context-specific associations. For example, while grit and learner confidence were significant predictors of resilience in South African studies, they were typically embedded within latent constructs in Indian studies and showed weaker or inconsistent links to achievement.

Contextual differences also shape how risk and protective factors operate. Caste identity and language status played a more prominent role in Indian studies, whereas linguistic, and school socio-economic differentials were more salient in South African work. These divergences point to the need for context-sensitive approaches to studying and supporting academic resilience.

This paper makes three key contributions to the literature on academic resilience. First, while much of the existing research adopts a largely universalist perspective (Ye et al., 2024; Rudd et al., 2021), this study undertakes a context-specific comparative analysis of the correlates of academic resilience in two countries shaped by severe and enduring educational inequalities. Second, by applying Rutter's (1987) Risk and Protective Factors framework to existing South African and Indian studies, this paper identifies mechanisms of resilience that are context-dependent but may be obscured in broader, cross-national studies. Finally, the review points to the need for more methodological and theoretical coherence to support comparative work and a more nuanced understanding of academic resilience and how it could be fostered among children and adolescents in these two countries.

2. Defining academic resilience

The concept of academic resilience spans multiple disciplines, attracting the interest of psychologists, sociologists, economists, and educators. Early work, largely rooted in psychology, conceptualised resilience as a fixed personality trait - an innate capacity to cope with adversity (Anthony and Koupernik, 1974). More recent scholarship, however, reframed resilience as a dynamic and malleable process, one that can be cultivated

through supportive environments and targeted interventions (Rutter, 2012). This shift in conceptualisation has enabled the concept to gain traction in education research, where it is broadly understood as the phenomenon of learners achieving academic success despite facing significant socioeconomic disadvantage or adversity (Wang et al., 1994; Borman and Overman, 2004).

At its core, academic resilience brings together two interrelated elements: a student's socioeconomic background and their academic achievement (Ye et al. 2024, p2). However, the ways in which these dimensions are conceptualised and measured vary widely across studies (Ye et al., 2021; Rudd et al., 2021). For example, the forms of adversity encountered by students in rural schools in low-income countries differ markedly from those faced by students in urban schools in high-income settings. Similarly, what constitutes "better than expected" academic performance is shaped by national, regional, and institutional expectations. This contextual variation helps explain the inconsistencies in findings across the literature and highlights the value of localising the study of academic resilience.

Methods used to operationalise academic resilience also vary substantially across studies as reflected in systematic reviews (Tutor and Spray, 2018; Rudd et al. 2021; Zheng et al. 2023). In Rudd et al.'s (2021) systematic review, they identify three main approaches to the measurement of academic resilience measurement. The definition-driven approach classifies students as resilient based on fixed thresholds for disadvantage (or adversity) and academic success. The process-driven approach treats resilience as a continuum, typically identifying disadvantaged students and assessing resilience based on relative academic performance. The latent construct approach, by contrast, infers resilience from associated traits or behaviours measured in scales, without directly measuring academic achievement. We draw on this classification to compare how resilience is operationalised across studies.

3. Theoretical framework to comparatively examine risk and protective factors

To comparatively examine how risk and protective factors are associated with academic resilience, this paper adopts Rutter's (1987) Risk and Protective Factors Model. According to this framework, learners are exposed to a combination of risk factors, which increase the likelihood of poor academic outcomes, and protective factors, which buffer against these risks and promote positive achievement. Risk factors may include poverty, exposure to violence, poor health, or lack of basic services. Protective factors encompass a range of individual, familial, and school-level supports including strong relationships with teachers, positive school climates, social support networks, and personal attributes like motivation and perseverance.

4. Contextual Overview

Learners in both South Africa and India face a multitude of risk factors that undermine their likelihood of academic success. These risks are deeply embedded in each country's historical and social structures, and continue to shape access to quality education today.

In both countries, historical systems of social stratification - apartheid in South Africa and the caste system in India - have left enduring legacies that continue to influence educational outcomes. In South Africa, apartheid was formally implemented between 1948 and 1994, but its roots in racial and economic exclusion stretch back to the colonial era beginning in 1652. Despite the political dismantling of apartheid over three decades ago, its effects remain visible in patterns of educational and social inequality (Gruitjers, Elbers and Reddy, 2024). In India, the caste system has persisted for millennia, with rigid social hierarchies institutionalised for over two thousand years (Dumont, 1980). In contrast to segregationist regimes imposed by colonial or minority elites, India's caste system was maintained through internal social reproduction and deeply rooted religious and cultural traditions, which helps explain its durability beyond its formal abolition in 1950 (Vallabhaneni, 2015).

Both countries' education systems remain profoundly unequal. In South Africa, the legacy of apartheid is starkly evident in learning outcomes: learners attending wealthy schools are ten times more likely to learn to read with meaning by the end of grade 4 than learners in disadvantaged schools (Böhmer & Wills, 2025). Language policy further entrenches inequality. Although most South African learners speak an African language at home, the language of instruction typically shifts to English or Afrikaans after Grade 3, which many students do not understand well enough to be able to access the curriculum (Spaull, 2016). This reinforces racial and socioeconomic disparities, as previously disadvantaged learners are often forced to learn in a language they neither speak fluently nor read proficiently.

Language constitutes an important dimension of educational inequality in India. Historical and institutional processes have conferred high status on languages such as English, which are closely associated with access to elite schooling and higher education, while many regional and non-dominant languages are linked to historically marginalised communities (Dwivedi, 2024).

Spatial inequalities further exacerbate educational disparities in both countries. In rural areas, access to quality schools, qualified teachers, and learning materials remains limited (Agrawal, 2014; McKay, 2019; Munje, 2018; Sumida and Kawata, 2021).

While both countries are characterised by deeply entrenched inequality, important differences remain. India's caste system is centuries older and more culturally embedded, whereas South Africa's apartheid regime, implemented in the last century by a minority group, was an externally imposed system of racial segregation. Their education systems also differ: India's decentralised governance leads to major regional disparities (Drèze and Sen, 2013), while South Africa has a centralised system with uneven implementation across provinces (Spaull, 2013).

Despite these contextual differences, in both settings education remains the primary pathway to upward social mobility. As such, understanding which factors support

academic resilience can inform strategies to mitigate systemic disadvantage and improve outcomes for marginalised students.

5. Method

The systematic collection of articles followed an adaptation of Rudd et al.'s (2021) review of measurement approaches of academic resilience and aligns with elements of the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009). Four academic databases were searched. First, EBSCOHost: Education Source, the Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), and APA PsychNet were searched using the terms ("India" OR "Indian" OR "South Africa" OR "South African") AND abstract:("academic resilience" OR "educational resilience").

Google Scholar was also searched to collect grey literature and in consideration that many Indian journals are not indexed in the other databases. Rudd et al. (2021) limited this search to articles with ("academic resilience" OR "educational resilience") in the title. Further limiting this search to papers with the country names in the title would miss many papers; however, including the search terms in the body of the paper resulted in more than 6,000 results, the vast majority of which were irrelevant (for example, a study which cites South African research but is based in another geographic location). To resolve this situation, the 6,000 results from Google Scholar were sorted by relevance and inspected sequentially until 20 consecutive studies failed to meet the inclusion criteria. This was done to gain sufficient coverage while avoiding the need to manually inspect every paper.

Initial inclusion criteria were articles which collected quantitative data from India or South Africa; were written in the English language; and were published between 2000 and January 2025. Examples of articles excluded at this screening stage are Wu et al. (2019), whose research included American Indians; Cloete and Ballard (2012) who studied academic resilience in South Africa using qualitative data from focus groups; and Nimisha et al. (2018) who conducted a meta-analysis of predictors of academic

resilience. At this stage, the inclusion criteria were applied when inspecting the abstracts of the paper.

Almost fifty articles passed the first screening and all but two could be accessed. A second screening was then applied by inspecting the body of the papers. At this second screening stage, following Rudd et al. (2021), articles had to either measure academic resilience using educational assessments or using a resilience scale specifically targeted to the educational domain: i.e. studies using a general resilience scale were to be omitted, even when the study was situated in an academic context, such as Habib (2019). Additionally, the sample in the studies must include youth of primary or secondary school age. Studies which sampled only students older than 19 were excluded, but those which had a sample spanning secondary school ages and older than 19 were included. For example, Mapaling et al. (2024) was excluded because they investigated academic resilience among engineering undergraduates in a South African university, whereas DUBY et al. (2022) was included because they studied the enrolment and drop-out of students aged 15-24¹. After the screening, 27 articles were included for the review (Figure 1).

¹ Also omitted was one study which investigated the academic resilience of deaf students using online learning during COVID-19 (Adigun and Ndwanwe, 2022). This study focused on issues related only to deaf students, and while valuable, does not lie within the scope of the present review.

Figure 1: The systematic literature collection process used in this study

Key features of each study were identified and documented. With respect to the sample, these features were: the sample size, the sample ages, and notable restrictions on making generalisations from the sample, e.g. Himna's (2024) study of only students with emigrant fathers. We also make note of how exposure to risk or adversity was dealt with, if at all in each paper. The measure of academic resilience was identified and classified as definition-driven, process-driven, or latent construct based on Rudd et al.'s (2021) methodological framework. Other scales were also noted, along with the type of statistical analyses conducted with academic resilience as a variable. Independent variables in the statistical analyses, as determinants of academic resilience, were also catalogued with a note of their statistical significance. Where available, risk and

protective factors of academic resilience in each study were then grouped into individual, family, school, peer, and community factors, following Ye et al. (2024).

6. Results

6.1 Geographical reach

As shown in Table 1, more than four-fifths of the studies were located in India, with only five studies from South Africa. Except for Das (2019) who uses nationally representative data, most of the Indian studies rely on small samples but they collectively cover a broad geographical base. Of the five South African studies, one draws on a nationally representative sample of primary level students (Hofmeyr, 2019).

6.2 Conceptualisation of academic resilience and statistical techniques used

A key distinction between the Indian and South African studies lies in how academic resilience is conceptualised and measured. All five South African studies employed definition- or process-driven approaches, typically identifying academically resilient learners as those performing above expectations despite socioeconomic disadvantage. But in defining performance that exceeds expectations, thresholds of expectation may differ from one study to the next. In contrast, the majority - 18 of 22 - Indian studies use latent construct approaches, relying on self-reported behaviours and attitudes associated with resilience, often without directly measuring academic achievement or disadvantage. Nine of the Indian studies rely on an academic resilience scale developed by Mallik and Kaur (2015). While this supports consistency within the academic resilience discipline in India, these studies typically employ simple correlational analysis so that while levels of academic resilience are identified, the studies individually say little about the risk or protective factors that foster academic resilience.

Of the 22 Indian studies reviewed, only one included student socio-economic status (SES) as a control (Das, 2019), five focused on socioeconomically disadvantaged samples, but the remaining 16 did not account for disadvantage or adversity at all.

Without defining how samples experience or are defined by adversity or disadvantage, this raises questions about whether many of these studies are measuring academic resilience - or something closer to academic buoyancy (Martin and Marsh, 2008), which reflects short-term coping (or handling every day setbacks) rather than long-term success in the face of structural adversity. These differences should be kept in mind when interpreting the results described in the remainder of this section.

The statistical approaches applied across the studies in both countries were limited in their utility. The use of basic correlational analysis, chi-square tests or t-tests of differences in academic resilience across two groups dominated in the studies. Where correlational analysis was relied upon, the theoretical direction of the association is often not clarified. For example, academic resilience may be a predictor of self-regulation or vice versa. In relying on bivariate correlational or descriptive statistics, identified associations are confounded by various other factors.

In just a few cases (Singh and Mukherjee, 2018; Das, 2019; Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019; Hofmeyr 2019), multivariate estimation of academic resilience is undertaken. Only a few studies provide coefficient estimates (with reported statistical significance) to identify risk or protective factors. Since this review relies on statistical significance to identify the factors which are likely to be determinants of academic resilience, multivariate studies are weighted more heavily in the findings.

None of the 27 studies identifies any causal relationships between academic resilience and protective or risk factors. This is a major shortcoming of the existing literature on academic resilience in these two countries.

Table 1: Key details of the reviewed articles

Paper	Country	Sample (n; age; other details)	Academic Resilience		Analysis approach
			Measure of disadvantage or adversity	Measure of academic resilience	
(Annalakshmi, 2015)	India	1451 students; 14-19 years	Rural educational district with low SES	Composite score of the Subjective Well-being Inventory (Sell and Nagpal, 1992); the Risk Survey Inventory (Annalakshmi, 2020), and academic achievement	Regression
(Mallick and Kaur, 2016)	India, 3 Punjab districts	600 students; Senior secondary	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	Correlation; DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender differences)
(JJ and Vijayalaxmi, 2017)	India, Bangalore city	50 students; 13-16 years	Not indicated	Subset of Adolescent Resilience Scale 2017 (unidentified)	DV in paired-sample t-tests (pre- and post-assessment differences)
(Rajan et al., 2017)	India, Malabar, Kerala	155 students; 14-16 years (secondary school)	Not indicated	5-C model of Academic Resilience (A. J. Martin and Marsh, 2006)	Correlation
(Singh and Mukherjee, 2018)	India, Andhra Pradesh	1008 students; cohort turned 19 by 2013	Pro-poor sample	Secondary school completion	Probit regression (multivariate)
(Dar and Chakraborty, 2019)	India, schools in Jammu and Kashmir	275 students in 3 schools; Grades 8-9	Jammu and Kashmir state: a "hostile and non-conducive academic environment"	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender differences)
(Das, 2019)	India, nationally representative	India Human Development Survey 2005; +/12300	Various SES and social group indicators	Reading and arithmetic grades	DV in logistic regression (multivariate)

		children, 8-11 years			
(Mohan and Verma, 2020)	India, public schools of Patiala, Ludhiana (Punjab) and Chandigarh	162 students; 15-20 years	No indicated	Motivation and Engagement Scale High School (MES-HS) (A. Martin, 2002). Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire	Correlation (focus on self-regulated learning strategies)
(Habeeb, 2021)	India, Aurangabad city	500 students in 10 schools; Senior secondary; English medium schools	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	Descriptive statistics (focus on gender differences)
(Mohan and Kaur, 2021)	India, Chandigarh, Ludhiana and Phagwara.	120 students; 13-18 years; Private schools	Not indicated	Motivation and Engagement Scale High School (MES-HS) (A. Martin, 2002)	Correlation (focus on grit vs. academic resilience dimensions)
(Appukuttan and Mathur, 2022)	India, schools from cities of Ahmedabad (Gujarat) and Kottayam (Kerala)	140 students; 14-18 years	Online learners during COVID-19	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender differences)
(Chitra and Binuraj, 2022)	India, 2 districts of Kerala	200 students from 4 schools; Secondary school	No indicated	Own-developed scale of academic resilience	Correlation; DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender and self-efficacy)
(Dixit and Vig, 2023)	India, Ludhiana city	480 students in 6 private schools; Grades 11-12	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	Descriptive statistics (assess levels of academic resilience across different tracks of students)

(Hashmi and Shakir, 2023)	India, Lucknow district, Uttar Pradesh	320 students in government and private secondary schools	Not indicated	Own-developed scale of academic resilience	Correlation; DV in independent t-tests (focus on academic anxiety and gender)
(R. Kaur and Kaur, 2023)	India, Amritsar district, Punjab	488 students in 6 schools; Grade 11	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	Correlation (focus on academic achievement scale, and gender)
(Appukuttan et al., 2024)	India, cities of Ahmedabad (Gujarat) and Kottayam (Kerala)	180; 14-18 years	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	Correlation (focus on learning styles)
(Chutia and Swargiary, 2024)	India, Jorhat district, Assam	101 in 3 government schools; Grade 10	Not indicated	Own-developed scale of academic resilience	Correlation (focus on parenting style)
(Himna, 2024)	India, Malappuram	560; Grade 9	Students with emigrant fathers but SES not indicated	Academic achievement score above 75 th percentile	DV in logistic regression, chi-square tests (consider various home and learner related factors)
(M. Kaur, 2024)	India, Ludhiana district, Punjab	200 students in 10 schools; Senior secondary	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale (K. Kaur and Singh, 2016)	Correlation (focus on parental involvement)
(Lalthanpuii and Lalhriatpuii, 2024)	India, 4 Mizoram districts (Aizawl, Mait, Serchhip, and Kolasib)	800; Senior secondary	Not indicated	Academic Resilience Scale: ARS-MMKS (Mallick and Kaur, 2015)	DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender differences)
(Nanda et al., 2024)	India (purposive sampling in authors area)	292; Under 21 years; school and college-going students	Experienced inter-state or inter-country migration but SES not indicated	The Academic Resilience Scale: ARS (30) (Cassidy, 2016)	Correlation (focus on culture shock)

(Ali and Kumar, 2025)	India, Al-Ameen Mission Belpukur, West Bengal	146; Grade 10	This institution was founded to empower students who lack financial resources	Academic Resilience Scale (Munmi and Yeasmin, 2023)	DV in independent t-tests (focus on gender)
(Mampane and Huddle, 2017)	South Africa, 2 schools	53 students in 2 schools; Grades 9 - 11	Rural schools	English, siSwati and Life Orientation results	DV in independent t-tests (focus on tracking student results)
(Herrero Romero et al., 2018)	South Africa, samples from the Western Cape and Mpumalanga	599; 16-18 years	Black students from socio-economically disadvantaged communities	Educational delay: out of school or at least one year behind	Descriptive statistics (chi-square tests/ANOVA) (examine various risk/protective factors)
(Hofmeyr, 2019)	South Africa, nationally representative	9572; Grade 4 (PIRLS); 9,316; Grade 9, (TIMSS)	SES measure	Reading and mathematics grades 1.5 s.d. above expectation based on SES	DV in logistic regression (multivariate)
(Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019)	South Africa, 60 township and rural schools in 3 provinces	2379; Grade 6	Students from rural or township schools, SES measure	Reading achievement 1.5 standard deviations above expectation based on SES	DV in logistic regression (multivariate)
(Dubey et al., 2022)	South Africa, 6 districts from 6 provinces	515 females; 15-24 years; during COVID-19	6 districts with high rates of HIV & socio-economic hardship; SES measure	Education enrolment and drop-out	Relative risk of education disruption

Notes: SES = socio-economic status, DV = dependent variable.

6.3 Predictors of academic resilience

The predictors of academic resilience in this review were categorised into broader protective factors in line with Ye et al.'s (2024) framework. Only a handful of studies examine a broad range of potential predictors, typically using multivariate regression models (e.g., Singh and Mukherjee, 2018; Das, 2019; Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019), while the

majority focused on the association between only one or two variables and academic resilience. About 9 of the identified Indian studies focus almost exclusively on documenting levels of academic resilience and how this differs by gender. Studies employing multivariate approaches are referenced more frequently in our synthesis of risk and protective factors, as their findings account for potential confounding variables and offer greater confidence in the independent effects of specific predictors.

6.3.1 Gender (Individual factors)

Findings on gender and academic resilience differ between India and South Africa. In India, most studies report no significant differences in overall resilience between boys and girls (Dar and Chakraborty, 2019; Appukuttan and Mathur, 2022; Hashmi and Shakir, 2023; Lalthanpuii and Lalhriatpuii, 2024; Ali and Kumar, 2025), though boys sometimes show higher attainment or completion (Singh and Mukhujee, 2018; Habeeb, 2021), and girls often score higher on socio-emotional dimensions such as emotional regulation and academic anxiety (Appukuttan and Mathur, 2022; Hashmi and Shakir, 2023; Lalthanpuii and Lalhriatpuii, 2024). In contrast, nationally representative data from South Africa show that girls are more academically resilient than boys (particularly in achieving higher than expected reading outcomes), even after accounting for socioeconomic and school-level factors (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019; Hofmeyr, 2019). This association is stronger among more socio-economically disadvantaged students.

6.3.2 Socio-emotional skills, attitudes and aspirations (individual factors)

Grit, defined as "perseverance and passion for long-term goals" (Duckworth, 2016) emerged as a significant protective factor in South Africa (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019). In a small study in India, most of the components of Academic Resilience (self-belief, persistence and anxiety) are found to be significantly correlated with Grit (Mohan and Kaur, 2021) although grit and resilience are closely connected constructs in support of goal attainment. Confidence is a very strong predictor of academic resilience in South

Africa (Hofmeyr, 2019), whereas in India, it was part of the construct itself, showing mixed associations with achievement - small but significant in one study (Appukuttan and Mathur, 2022) and non-significant in another (Dixit and Vig, 2023). Self-efficacy was consistently linked to academic resilience in Indian studies, with strong and significant effects reported (Chitra and Binuraj, 2022; Himna, 2024; Rajan et al., 2017; Singh and Mukherjee, 2018).

Attitudes toward school also mattered. In South Africa, positive school attitudes and enjoyment of subjects like reading and mathematics were significant protective factors, though effects varied by language and school socio-economic quintile (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019; Hofmeyr, 2019). In India, enjoyment of school was one of the strongest measured predictors of academic resilience in a nationally representative study (Das, 2019).

Using India's Guna framework, Annalakshmi (2015) found that a Sattvic temperament - marked by clarity and harmony - was positively associated with resilience in rural public schools, while Rajasic (controlling) and Tamasic (apathetic) traits were risk factors. The same study found that extrinsic aspirations (wealth, fame) were negatively associated with resilience, while academic aspirations were non-significant possibly due to the overlap with self-concept in the model. In contrast, academic aspirations were a significant protective factor in South Africa (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019), and intrinsic motivation was a significant predictor in one Indian study (Himna, 2024).

6.3.3 Home background (family)

In terms of material support, the number of books at home was non-significant in South Africa (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019). DUBY et al. (2022) present a complex picture in South Africa during the Covid-19 pandemic, where risk factors include lack of cell phone access and not eating for a day due to lack of food, however cell phone use, household electricity, and internet access did not have a statistically significant relationship with remaining enrolled in school.

Living with biological parents was one of the few variables that is comparable for the two countries. This was a significant protective factor in both India and South Africa (Duby et al., 2022; Herrero et al., 2018). Additionally, engaging in authoritative and democratic parenting styles was found to have positive associations with academic resilience in India, in contrast to non-significant associations for authoritarian, permissive, and negligent parenting styles (Himna, 2024).

Although family structure is not easily changed, this highlights the need for additional support for students experiencing household instability (Aleghfeli & Nag, 2024).

6.3.4 School factors

Structural features of schools had an association with academic resilience in some instances. In India, smaller class size was a protective factor for reading outcomes (Das, 2019) but this was not the case for South Africa, where no association was found (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019). However, school size (i.e. total number of students in a school) was a significant predictor among a South African student sample, with larger schools associated with a lower likelihood of being academically resilient (Herrero Romero et al., 2018). School resources (such as having computers) supported higher than expected performance in poorer schools in South Africa (Hofmeyr, 2019).

To some extent elements of the school environment were associated with academic resilience in India and South Africa. Bullying and rejection were risk factors for academic resilience in India (Annalakshmi, 2015) and for higher than expected academic performance in South Africa (Hofmeyr, 2019).

A relatively high rate of teacher absence was a significant risk factor in South Africa (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019) and having a specialist language teacher was a protective factor (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019). Interestingly, teacher qualifications were non-significant in South Africa (Hofmeyr, 2019). No comparative teacher variables were found in the Indian studies, apart from teacher kindness and this was positively associated with

academic resilience (Das, 2019). However, Das (2019, p719) concludes that “schools fail to play the expected role of being the source of resilience among those who face the strongest burden of structural factors” whereas child level and household level factors play a more important role.

6.3.5 Peers and community factors

As in Ye et al. (2024), there were few studies which looked at peer or community factors associated with academic resilience. In India, Himna (2024) found a significant relationship between academic test scores and peer relationships and social competence for students with emigrant fathers. Engagement in peer learning was also a significant protective factor, as measured by each dimension of a motivation and engagement scale. Finally, “relationships with peers and adults” is a dimension of the Academic Resilience Scale of Mallick and Kaur (2015) and one Indian study found a very high correlation (.96) of this variable with an academic achievement score (Appukuttan & Mathur, 2022), while another study found only a small (.21) correlation (Kaur & Kaur, 2023).

Finally, cultural identity - often tied to geography - emerged as a critical contextual factor. In India, caste or social group moderated the effects of predictors like confidence and school support (Das, 2019), while in South Africa, predictors significantly varied across language groups and by the socio-economic level of a school (Hofmeyr, 2019).

7. Discussion

In summary, research on academic resilience in South Africa and India faces both methodological and theoretical limitations. Most Indian studies rely on small, non-representative samples, with only one using a nationally representative dataset, while South African studies are few, and only one draws on a nationally representative sample. Measurement approaches vary: South African studies define resilience in terms of performance above expectations despite disadvantage, but thresholds differ across

studies, whereas Indian studies largely use latent scales without directly measuring academic achievement. These divergent approaches reflect different disciplinary traditions and make direct comparisons difficult.

Surprisingly, only a minority of studies account for socioeconomic status or focus on disadvantaged populations (or define the adversity faced by samples), raising questions about whether these studies capture academic resilience or academic buoyancy. Statistical analyses are dominated by simple correlations or descriptive statistics, with few using multivariate models and none establishing causal relationships, leaving both the magnitude and direction of associations unclear and potentially confounded.

Theoretical limitations are closely linked to these methodological issues. Common theoretical frameworks are seldom used across studies in conceptualising the link between academic resilience and risk or protective factors. Resilience is also frequently examined in relation to a very narrow set of these factors, limiting analysis of how multiple forms of protection interact under conditions of disadvantage. Although a wide range of factors were explored across studies, relatively few of the same factors were examined in both India and South Africa.

Despite these limitations, we found some points of comparison and divergence in protective factors. Among the common findings on individual factors, grit emerged as a significant protective factor in South Africa but in India it was often embedded in latent constructs of academic resilience. These findings align with international evidence on the contribution of grit to academic outcomes (Cassidy, 2016; Thorsen et al., 2021; Saifullah and Khan, 2022). Enjoyment of learning emerged as a consistent protective factor across both countries. Widely supported in both international (Cheung et al., 2014; García-Crespo et al., 2022) and local studies, it is likely to be mutually reinforcing with achievement (Putwain et al., 2018; Martin and Marsh, 2006). Living with a biological parent was a significant protective factor in both countries, in line with evidence from

other countries (Cheung et al., 2014; Langenkamp, 2010).

Commonly studied across the 27 studies, gender has varied associations with academic resilience in India among children and adolescents, but in South Africa girls are found to be more academically resilient on average than boys (Wills & Hofmeyr, 2019).

Although individual factors emerge more commonly as predictors of academic resilience, cultural and contextual factors associated with inequality in each country shape academic resilience in meaningful ways. Caste in India and language or socio-economic groupings in South Africa shape patterns of academic resilience, where associations with protective factors vary significantly along these group dimensions.

7.1. Implications

These findings suggest three potential policy directions that could help foster academic resilience among disadvantaged learners in India and South Africa. First, promoting enjoyment of learning could support academic resilience. Strategies might include improving classroom engagement through learner-centred pedagogy. Second, our findings suggest a need to offer additional support to learners experiencing family instability - for example, through mentorship programmes, psychosocial services, or school-based counselling. However, interventions must be tailored to local contexts, accounting for the complex interplay of socioeconomic, cultural, and school-level factors that shape learners' experiences.

7.2. Contributions

This study contributes to the academic resilience literature by synthesising evidence regarding the protective and risk factors that support academic resilience in South Africa and India. In narrowing the focus to similar settings, it aimed to provide more context-specific insights than broader country comparative studies. Yet, the study demonstrates that even when narrowing our focus to just two countries, comparative constraints are

encountered due to varied (and often limited) methodological approaches used in academic resilience research in these two countries.

7.3. Advancing the scholarship on academic resilience in India and South Africa

Advancing academic resilience research in India and South Africa may require the development and more consistent use of common theoretical frameworks and conceptual measurement approaches that are rooted in the specific conditions of these contexts. Much of the literature on academic resilience - and the analytical tools it employs - emerge from, and reflect the assumptions of, educational systems in high-income countries (Zheng et al. 2023). Such frameworks may offer limited explanatory power where educational trajectories are shaped by distinct historical and institutional conditions or structural inequalities.

While academic resilience scales developed in the context of India (Mallick and Kaur, 2015) are available and widely used in various studies, academic resilience scales have not been widely applied or tested among school-goers in South Africa. Future studies in both contexts should be designed to measure a wider set of protective and risk factors to examine their relationship with academic resilience, while adopting analytical approaches that support causal interpretation.

Mixed-methods designs that collect academic achievement data while measuring academic resilience constructs and broader sets of protective and risk factors would allow for more nuanced analyses of how different aspects of resilience interact. In turn, this would support more comparative work across studies and inform more targeted, context-appropriate interventions.

8. Conclusion

By synthesising the quantitative evidence on academic resilience among children and adolescents in India and South Africa, the review highlights both shared and divergent

risk and protective factors. Enjoyment of learning and family structure emerged as consistent predictors of resilience, while notable contextual differences - such as the role of language, caste, and operational definitions of resilience - complicate direct comparisons. These findings emphasise the importance of locally grounded approaches to supporting academic resilience, while also raising questions about how resilience is comparatively measured and understood across settings. Future research should aim to harmonise definitions and integrate mixed methods to better capture the multidimensional and context-specific nature of resilience.

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